

Entrepreneurship Education as a Pre-Requisite for Graduate Entrepreneurship: A Study of Graduate Entrepreneurs in Yenagoa City

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Abstract—The concepts of entrepreneurship education together with graduate entrepreneurship have taken centre stage in many countries as a 21st century strategy for economic growth and development. Entrepreneurship education has been viewed as a pre-requisite tool for a more effective and successful business operation. This paper seeks to verify if entrepreneurship education is pre-requisite to graduate entrepreneurship, and to ascertain if such other factors as the need for achievement, competence and experience etc. also play a foundational role in the choice of a graduate becoming an entrepreneur. The scope of the research study is entrepreneurs within Yenagoa metropolis in Bayelsa state, Nigeria. The sample target is graduates engaged in entrepreneurship activities (graduates who own and run businesses). Stratified sampling technique was used and 101 responses were obtained from a total of 300 questionnaires issued. Bar chart, tables and percentages were used to analyze the collected data. The findings revealed that personality traits, situational circumstance, need for achievement and experience/competence were the foundational factors stimulating graduate entrepreneurs to engage in entrepreneurial pursuits. Of all, personality trait showed the highest score with 73 (73%) out of 101 entrepreneurs agreeing. Experience/Competence and situational circumstances followed behind with 66 (65%) and 63 (62.4%), respectively. Entrepreneurship education revealed the least score with 33 (32.3%) out of 101 participating entrepreneurs. All hope, however, is not lost, as this shows that something can be done to increase the impact of entrepreneurship education on graduate entrepreneurship.

Keywords—Creative destruction, entrepreneurs, entrepreneurship education, graduate entrepreneurship, pre-requisite.

I. INTRODUCTION

NIGERIA, as a country, is witnessing massive turnout of graduates every year. With over 150 Institutions of Higher Learning (IsHL) across the country, over 500,000 graduates emerge every year from diverse disciplines besides those who studied abroad and come back to the country to hustle for jobs [1] of which between 150,000 and 200,000 graduates are churned out from universities alone each year [2], [3]. According to Dr. Charles Ugwu, the Director, Professional Development Directorate, Chartered Institute of Personnel Management, out of these huge numbers that graduate every year, only as few as 20% get employed by

organizations [2]. In another report, it is recorded that no less than 5.3 million Nigerian youths were jobless as at 2014, while an alarming total of 1.8 million graduates enter the labour market yearly [4]. However, this number contradicts the number reported by Nda-Isaiah in 2013 when it was reported to be 40 million unemployed youths in the country [3]. The International Centre for Investigative Reporting (ICIR) also reported that an estimated 17 million Nigerian professionals are available in every field in diaspora, no doubt the country could be construed to have the required human resources for her growth and development and inclusion in the league of top 20 biggest economies in the world [5]-[8]. However, the report from a nationwide survey co-sponsored by the Tertiary Education Trust Fund and Nigeria Universities Commission with a focus on graduate employability, it was revealed that 44% of the more than 20 corporate firms and 100 persons interviewed were of the opinion that Nigerian graduates are average in creativity and competence, 63% rated them as average on leadership skills, while 56% considered the graduates as average in innovativeness. On skills that are prerequisite like oral communication and report writing, entrepreneurial, problem solving, information technology, analytical and even decision making, 60% of the interviewees rated graduates as poor. In the final analysis, the researchers concluded by saying “*Nigerian graduates lack the capacity... to be employed and so are “simply unemployable”* [9].

If all these qualities that should be gained through university education is lacking in the Nigerian graduates, what is then missing for graduates to attain these qualities? Fems used the term “functional education” which he described as a process by which students are equipped with occupational skills and competencies “*that will enable them become self-reliant, adept in living, entrepreneurial, creative and innovative in problem solving, and contributing members towards their society’s economic development, as being lacking in the educational system*” as cited in [10]. In his view, entrepreneurship education (EE) is critical to achieving functional education as it will stimulate entrepreneurial thinking in graduates, and thereby produce graduate entrepreneurs. In this research, the term ‘graduate entrepreneurs’ is used to mean graduates that venture into business ownership and management. Graduates in this context refer to those in possession of a Doctorate, Master’s, a Bachelor’s degree, or even HND or its equivalent, in any field of study. It is believed that the entrepreneurial quality of the graduate entrepreneur is critical in the survival, thriving, as

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well as sustenance of a business venture. Graduate entrepreneurship has been receiving increased attention in recent times especially because of the ongoing recession in the global economy which is pushing more graduates towards entrepreneurial engagements [11]-[13]. As a result, the Government of Nigeria introduced EE as a compulsory course of study in all Nigeria Institutions of Higher Learning with the hope that it will solve the unemployment problems and engender job creation by graduates rather than job seeking, thereby creating wealth for themselves, and in the process developing the economy as a whole [11].

The purpose of this paper is to ascertain whether EE is a pre-requisite for graduate entrepreneurship, the success of entrepreneurial engagements and the quality of such entrepreneurs using Yenagoa: a rural-urban city in Nigeria as the scope of study. The paper explores entrepreneurship and the entrepreneur to understand both concepts from diverse perspectives. Then EE and its importance in the Nigerian context are discussed. Thirdly, EE and the development of graduate entrepreneurs are discussed from the available literature. Finally, the findings were discussed and measured against literature and recommendations made on the way forward.

II. BRIEF BACKGROUND OF YENAGOA

Yenagoa is a small rural-urban city located in Bayelsa state in the South-South Niger Delta region of Nigeria with a population of over 550,000 people. Commercial activities are increasing day by day, as people migrate continually from the rural areas and other much developed cities to do business in Yenagoa, which is the capital city of Bayelsa state. Currently, there is no available information as to the estimated number of businesses registered in Yenagoa, but it is estimated that there are well over 1,000 businesses that operate in the city, including trading activities.

III. ENTREPRENEURSHIP AND ENTREPRENEURS

Entrepreneurship is crucial for the growth and development of any economy as it is regarded as the “engine” for innovation that drives economic advancement, job and wealth creation [14]-[16]; as the dynamic process of creating or transforming an organization for the singular purpose of creating new products/services or adding value to existing products/services through the skilful coordination of resources [17] and, as the indispensable lever to cope with the new competitive economic landscape Hitt and Reed cited in [15]. However, the creative and innovative ingenuity of entrepreneurs to transform ideas into profitable business conglomerates have attracted the attention of both academics and policy makers to take another look at entrepreneurship. In line with the increasing relevance of entrepreneurship, countries like Singapore, United Kingdom, Brazil, Australia, Malaysia and even India, since the 1990s have endorsed EE programmes into every level of their educational systems. In Malaysia for instance, entrepreneurship plays a very critical role as they envisage being a fully developed nation come

2020, and EE has been the catalyst of the growth of entrepreneurs [12]. Because of the dynamism of the process of entrepreneurship, it is essential that entrepreneurship be taught for the transference of its skills, competencies and knowledge from an expert to a protégé. As a result, there is a growing interest in the development and design of academic programmes to encourage and foster entrepreneurship in all levels of education. Finkle and Deeds [18] in their recent studies also observed that the demand for entrepreneurship centres and faculties have escalated extraordinarily during the last 10 years. Again, Kuratko and Hodgetts together emphasize that entrepreneurship:

“involves an application of energy and passion towards the creation of an enterprise and this includes the willingness to take calculative risks; team work; the creative skill to marshal needed resources; fundamental skill of building solid business plan; and finally, the vision to recognize opportunity where others see chaos, contradiction, and confusion” [16].

Entrepreneurship is more than being smart, it is the adeptness an individual possesses that enables an individual to collaborate with others and act in the face of opportunities and challenges. The European Commission Communication summarizes it this way:

“Entrepreneurship refers to an individual’s ability to turn ideas into action. It includes creativity, innovation and risk taking, as well as the ability to plan and manage projects in order to achieve objectives. This supports everyone in day-to-day life at home and in society, makes employees more aware of the context of their work and better able to seize opportunities, and provides a foundation for entrepreneurs establishing a social or commercial activity” [17, pp. 3].

Entrepreneurship however, cannot be discussed without the mention of two key elements as it does not function in a vacuum. These elements are: 1) the entrepreneur and 2) an enabling environment. Entrepreneurship has been described as the act of being an entrepreneur [19] and also as the service entrepreneurs render [20]. It is also viewed as a dynamic process towards increasing capitals: that is, a process which generates new components using creativity and innovation as a tool, and is achieved by using time and risks, etc. [21], [22]. In fact, according to Arasteh, entrepreneurship is an endless and rudimentary resource in all societies. Entrepreneurship is not anything else but a course of purposeful activity that fuses together creativeness, risks, innovation and personal success that requires the individual to take moral, financial and even social responsibility to set up structures to foster a profitable business idea. While there is no generally agreed upon definition of entrepreneurship, in this paper, we have defined it as “the primary catalyst for innovation” [23, pp. 351], and entrepreneurial engagement which is congruent with Schumpeter’s “creative destruction” that brings about drastic economic change [24, pp. 237].

According to Peter Drucker, entrepreneurship is impossible without an entrepreneur, thus defining an entrepreneur as a

person who creates something new, different, and is capable of shifting and transforming values [25]. Schumpeter describes the entrepreneur as a person who takes the initiative to design new combinations out of non/pre-existing things, consequently “*becoming a promoter of innovative progress; and a generator of economic progress*” [26, pp. 34]. The entrepreneur has also been viewed as an individual that possess certain abilities and skill sets to recognize and evaluate an opportunity, initiate a business plan, organizes and assembles other factors of production, bears all risks in order to take advantage of the opportunities and takes appropriate actions to ensure success [23], [27]; and as one who can convert what he loves doing into a money-making venture [28]. Hong et al. [29] classified the entrepreneur into two categories of persons: as a leader charged with the responsibility of decision-making and management in an organization and secondly, as a founder or innovator/inventor who takes risks to set up a new business venture.

Unlike many authors who view the entrepreneur as the risk bearer [21], [30] Schumpeter differs, he is of the opinion that the capitalist is the one that bears the risk while the entrepreneur “*reflects a kind of person willing to put his or her career and financial security on the line and take risks in the name of an idea, spending much time as well as capital (wealth created in other to create further wealth) on an uncertain venture*” cited in [31, pp. 197]. He sees the entrepreneur as an agent capable of combining human resources and opportunities into a productive organism [26]. Schumpeter speaks of these various groups of human resources as workers, financiers/funders, capitalists and landlords, but keeps them separate from the entrepreneur throughout his work. Nonetheless, taking into cognizance the uncertain nature of any business venture, the entrepreneur can be said to be a risk taker.

The skill sets and decisiveness of an entrepreneur are either in-born or learnt through experience or training. However, it is an agreed upon fact that not all entrepreneurs are born, some are trained. In congruence with this assertion, Drucker, noted for his out-of-the-box managerial thinking, stated that entrepreneurship “*is not magic, is not mysterious, and it has nothing to do with genes. It is a discipline. And like any discipline it can be learned*” [15, p. 2]. Therefore, training/education is a critical part of the development of entrepreneurs, as it is believed that the quality of the entrepreneur determines to a large extent the success of a business venture. In fact, there is a widespread idea that EE would produce more and better skilled and equipped entrepreneurs than has ever been in the past, and that education would increase the probability of attaining entrepreneurial success [32]; hence, the emergence of EE.

IV. ENTREPRENEURSHIP EDUCATION

The first recorded lecture on entrepreneurship was in 1938 at Kobe University, Japan by Shigeru Fijii. He was said to be the pioneer of entrepreneurship teaching. Afterwards, courses in small business management began to emerge in the 1940s

and then in 1947, Myles Mace of Harvard Business School introduced the first well-articulated entrepreneurship course in USA [15], [33]. Since then, EE has become popular and has expanded tremendously in most industrial economies, and is gaining much interest and wide acceptance amongst academics, policy makers and even industry professionals globally [34]. Entrepreneurship programmes are being proliferated in universities all over the world. This is symptomatic of the general belief and assumption that EE is a sustainable economic development strategy to help build and prepare individuals to be responsible and enterprising, and adept in unfathomable entrepreneurial thinking that will contribute to the economic growth and development of a nation. Irrespective of its widespread acceptance, there is no agreed upon definition of what EE means. Different institutions, academics and countries define the concept from differing points of views. Bechard and Toulouse view EE as “*a collection of formalized teachings that informs, trains and educates anyone interested in business creation or small business development*” [27, p. 216]. According to Osalor, EE is not a once and for all event rather it is “*a lifelong learning process, starting as early as elementary school and progressing through all levels of education, including adult education. Entrepreneurial education focuses on developing understanding and capacity for pursuit of entrepreneurial behaviours, skills and attributes in widely different contexts*” [28, p. 3].

The essence of EE therefore, is to alter the perception and attitude of the students and in the process, equip them with relevant and requisite knowledge, skill sets and motivation to promote entrepreneurial engagement in a multiplicity of settings, either to start own businesses or to manage another's. According to Hynes and Richardson [35], EE seeks to furnish students/protégés with fundamental knowledge, skills and competencies necessary to exploit opportunities in this increasingly knowledge-based economy. Some of the benefits of EE according to findings from University of Arizona [36] and [29] include:

- Entrepreneurship graduates are three times more likely to start up a new business venture.
- EE increased the probability of graduate business start-ups by 25%.
- Entrepreneurship graduates are three times more likely to be self-employed.
- Entrepreneurship graduates are more likely to be employed full time and less likely to work for government or non-profit organizations.
- Have annual incomes that are 27% higher and own 62% more assets.
- EE increases the earning capacity of graduates.
- Entrepreneurship graduates working for large firms earn 30% more and have job satisfaction more than their counterparts.
- They are more ready and better fortified to face obstacles head-on positively than non-entrepreneurship graduates.

Although there have been numerous studies proving the

positive effect of EE on the desirability to start a business and the feasibility of starting one for those who attended entrepreneurship programmes [16], [37], there is still very little empirical evidence of the positive impact of EE on graduate entrepreneurial success especially in Nigeria. Industrialists believe that mere entrepreneurial awareness is not enough for graduates to develop entrepreneurial practices. The development of entrepreneurial practices requires pragmatic pedagogical approaches capable of instilling transversal entrepreneurial skills. For scholars, it has been very difficult to ascertain clearly the effect education and training has on small and medium size enterprise (SME) performance, either at the start-up stage or other stages in their development [15].

V. EE IN NIGERIA

The focus on EE has never been more vital as it is today in Nigeria, especially as the country is threatened with enormous developmental challenges and crises that span across every sector of its economy. Even though the practice of entrepreneurship in Nigeria can be traced back to the days of 'trade by barter': *trading in the form of exchange where a farmer uses his farm produce as payment for the purchase of other farm produce he/she does not possess. It is usually done within a community, amongst farmers living within the same community* [38]. This focus is spurred by the recognition of the degree to which EE serves as a sustainable strategy for economic development, at least as evident in developed economies. Although formal EE is new and still very nascent in Nigeria: up until now, only very few IHL have started offering 'Entrepreneurship' as a major or a degree programme at undergraduate but none in postgraduate levels across the country, though programmes to educate youths/graduates for self-reliance and entrepreneurial pursuits have been initiated since the 1980s. In 1986 for instance, the 'National Directorate of Employment' (NDE) was birthed, followed by the establishment of 'Work For Yourself Programme' (WFYP) in 1987. Both the NDE and WFYP were joint programmes to offer training, foster entrepreneurship and offer financial assistance to start-up entrepreneurs. These programmes were instituted as a result of the collapse of Nigeria's economy which resulted in massive layoffs and retrenchment of workers, as well as high unemployment among youths. This experience marked the beginning of policies embracing entrepreneurship teachings in Nigeria [39]. Consequently in 2004, the National Universities Commission (NUC) introduced 'Entrepreneurship Development' as a course into the curriculum of Nigerian Universities, with the sole aim of challenging and equipping graduates with entrepreneurial skills and competencies. Then in 2007, entrepreneurship development became a compulsory module for every student in Nigeria's IsHL. Although there are a number of researchers in favour of the argument that EE could help Nigeria gravitate towards the achievement of Millennium Development Goals and Vision 2020 [12], 10 years of EE has passed but Nigerian graduates are yet to demonstrate their competence in creating

new business ventures. According to statistics from the Manpower Board and the Federal Bureau of Statistics, the country still lingers with a startling unemployment rate at over 70% of its 80 million youth population and poverty at over 70% [40]. Only a fraction of about 16% of young graduates have jobs not related to subsistent agriculture; thus, suggesting a waste of young, enthusiastic and talented graduates.

VI. EE AND GRADUATE ENTREPRENEURSHIP

In their research into entrepreneurial potential of secondary school and university students, Křištofiaková and Krelová assert that "*it is necessary to introduce the subject of entrepreneurship into all types of secondary schools and university programmes. Without the development of entrepreneurial skills, our graduates will not be able to succeed in the labour market*" [41, pp. 2]. They are of the opinion that EE is critical for the development of graduate entrepreneurs and should be thoroughly taught from primary to university level to instil entrepreneurship thinking in the students from early age. Graduate entrepreneurs in this paper refer to those graduates who own and/or manage their own businesses. Following the comment from Awogbenle and Iwuamadi resulting from their research findings, entrepreneurship development programmes (EDPs) in IsHL are most vital now for successful graduate entrepreneurship, and are of the opinion that EDPs can equip students with the requisite skills, resilience and competencies needed for productive, efficient and sustainable entrepreneurial engagement [42]. However, no matter how robust the EDP training programmes are, without adequate and corresponding provision for funding of incubators in university campuses and graduate start-ups, the programmes would turn out to be a mere waste of time and energy, and would lack what it takes to churn out graduate entrepreneurs as is seen in Nigeria today. There is broad acceptability that EE is a vital channel through which any nation can experience the springing up of quality entrepreneurs and new industries. It is assumed that the knowledge entrepreneurship graduates gains through EE programmes would enable them venture into businesses after graduation and equip them with the capability and resilience to overcome unemployment and business challenges by being resourceful, ingenious, innovative and persistent. It is also believed that EE has obvious effect on cultivating graduate entrepreneurship, enriching their knowledge of business processes and improved entrepreneurial qualities. Entrepreneurial quality in this paper is used to refer to all the essential characteristics that lead to entrepreneurial success. The quality of an entrepreneur is important as it will determine the success or failure of an enterprise. Contrary to the opinions of many scholars as regards EE being the prerequisite for entrepreneurial quality, Abd Rani and Hong [14] opine that, entrepreneurial quality is largely dependent on external environmental and psychological factors – family background, work experience, social support, pressures associated with unemployment, desire for achievement, creativity, competitiveness and self-interest, initiative and leadership,

locus of control and mentoring etc. However, they did not deny the relevant role university experience plays in boosting student entrepreneurial intention, and enhancing graduate entrepreneurial quality. Johannison is also of the opinion that, *“to teach individuals to become not only more enterprising, but businessmen as well...is an undertaking that in both time and scope is beyond the capabilities of an academic business school”* [26, p. 348]. The argument is that the skills traditionally taught in universities and the teaching approaches are essential, but not sufficient to make a successful graduate entrepreneur.

Student entrepreneurial intention, as used in this paper, is the intention a student has to start a business after graduation as a result of EE undertaken as a course during academic studies. Research has fully established the relationship between EE and students entrepreneurial intention; however, the rate to which intention has been transformed into action (actually starting a business after graduation) is yet to be ascertained, especially in Nigeria [17], [19], [42]-[44]. There is, however, paucity of rigorous empirical research to corroborate the claims of most universities that their students benefitted greatly from the EE programmes and have upon graduation gone to start-up new ventures. In relation to graduate business start-ups, Bass and Hatcher [45] after their survey of Meridian Community College, Mississippi, USA, reported that of the 157 out of 478 students that participated in the College’s JumpStart Entrepreneur Training Program: a 15-week EE scheme, over 67 started a new venture with the provision of a \$90,000 grant as start-up incentive, of which, 57 are still operating with over 80 jobs created. In another survey conducted in 1988 by Stirling University involving 5,375 graduates from 10 universities in Scotland and England, it was reported that 9.7% (about 521) of graduates in the research went on to become business owners within a period of five years after graduation. However, the researchers acknowledged that up to 20% of the graduates in the sample already had some measure of entrepreneurial experience before enrolling in the entrepreneurship courses, and that this prior experience gained before acquiring EE tends to greatly enhance their overall performance as entrepreneurs. The report also indicated that 78% of these entrepreneurs were still in business five years later, considering the high rate of business failures. Thus, opining that businesses owned and run by graduate entrepreneurs are better, more profitable and sustainable than those managed by non-graduates. Consequently, in another research covering a 10-year period (1997-2006) with a sample size of 64 students selected across eight universities in the United Kingdom, it was observed that as at the tenth year, eight had become sole traders, 31 had become micro-business owners, 16 owners of a small business, while five became partners in enterprises and four partnered in an established enterprise, thus totaling 64 [44]. A few other studies have also proven the relationship between EE and new business creation. A 50-year review of Young Enterprise in the United Kingdom also revealed substantial differences between those who had experienced enterprise and

EE (either at school or at university – the study does not distinguish) and those who did not, with 42% of Young Enterprise alumni being owners of a business (although not necessarily a start-up) compared to 26% of those in a control group with similar characteristics, but without EE. Also in Norway, it was found that 21% of 25-34 year olds that took part in the Young Enterprise programme have started their own businesses compared with 4.5% in this age group across the entire population [46]. Again, it was found that companies owned by EE graduates, in general, were larger and have more sales than those owned by non-EE graduates. In the case of Nigeria, no research has been made to reveal to the correlation between EE and graduate business start-up.

VII. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Descriptive survey design was used for this study to gather data from the field. The reason for its use is to collect detailed and factual information that describes and already prevailing phenomenon. The target population for this research was entrepreneurs within the Yenagoa metropolis that took entrepreneurship as a module during their course of study. All participants are graduates. A total of 300 questionnaires were distributed and 101 were returned. A stratified sampling technique was adopted. The questionnaire was primarily designed to realize the purposes of this research study.

TABLE I
 QUESTIONNAIRE DISTRIBUTION

Total Number Returned	Total Number Unreturned	Total Number Distributed
101	199	300

The questionnaire is divided into two segments, the first segment collected demographic information such as age, sex, occupation, educational background etc., and the second segment was divided further into five groups: Personality Traits, Need for Achievement, Situational, EE and Experience/Competence, with six questions in each group that measure the correlation of these factors with entrepreneurial engagements. A Likert scale of five points: strongly agree, agree, undecided, disagree and strongly disagree, was adopted. Of the 101 participants, 53 (52.5%) were male and 48 (47.5%) were female, while 67 (66.3%) range in age from 31-40 years and 34 (33.7%) range in age from 20-30 years. Fig. 1 is a bar chart showing the results from the research findings.

Fig. 1 shows a striking revelation. EE shows the least of all reasons for entrepreneurial engagement by graduates, while trait, need for achievement and situational circumstances were the most stimulating factors in graduate entrepreneurial engagement. Table I shows the number and percentage of the participants’ responses to the questions in the different parts of the second segment of the questionnaire.

In this analysis, we would combine the results of strongly agree and agree together, as well as disagree and strongly disagree to get the aggregate of positive and negative responses. Considering personality trait as a factor that stimulates entrepreneurial engagement, 73 (73%) of the 101

respondents agree that trait is the stimulating factor for entrepreneurial engagement; 55 (55.7%) of the participants suggest Need for Achievement; 63 (62.4%) are of the opinion that Situational Circumstance caused them to pursue entrepreneurship; another 66 (65%) selected Experience and Competence as a stimulating factor for engaging in entrepreneurship, while only 33 (32.3%) of the participants agree that EE was a stimulant in their pursuit of entrepreneurship. However, 63 (63.2%) of the participants are

of the opinion that EE had nothing to do with their decision to pursue business as a career path. Although the research findings cannot at this moment be generalized due to the scope of the study, the study shows a 32.3% positive correlation between EE and graduate entrepreneurial engagement, however, it is evident that, graduates engage more in entrepreneurship activities not because of the entrepreneurship programmes they attended while in school.

TABLE II
CUMULATIVE POINTS AND PERCENTAGES FROM THE LIKERT SCALE

S/N	Factors	Strongly Agree	Agree	Undecided	Disagree	Strongly Disagree
1	Personality Traits	33 (32.6%)	40 (40.4%)	5 (4.5%)	18 (18%)	5 (4.5%)
2	Need For Achievement	30 (30.2%)	25 (25.5%)	9 (8.4%)	28 (27.4%)	9 (8.4%)
3	Situational Circumstances	34 (33.8%)	29 (28.6%)	2 (2.3%)	14 (14.1%)	22 (21.2%)
4	EE	7 (6.7%)	26 (25.6%)	5 (4.5%)	29 (28.7%)	34 (34.5%)
5	Experience & Competence	37 (36.5%)	29 (28.5%)	7 (7%)	21 (21%)	7 (7%)

Fig. 1 Cumulative response from respondents

VIII. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

The findings from the research study are evident and show that there is more to be done to ensure EE in Nigeria is able to stimulate entrepreneurship engagement as we have seen in many other countries. Although the positive correlation is low, it shows that it is possible to improve the programme either by mode of teaching or beefing up the modules. As a result of the research findings, the following are recommended for further study.

- A study should be carried out to measure in a broader scale the impact of entrepreneurship teaching methods on graduate entrepreneurial engagement.
- A research should be conducted to evaluate the success of businesses run by graduates that took entrepreneurship courses and those that did not.
- A study should also be conducted to ascertain if businesses run by entrepreneurship graduates are larger in terms of income than those run by non-graduates.

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